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APPLICATION OF TWO-STAGE MCDM TECHNIQUES IN EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF ELECTRONIC PAYMENT SYSTEMS IN GHANA

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ABSTRACT

Electronic payment systems act as a catalyst in the economic development of many developing countries. However, their evaluation has become a daunting task over the years. This research employed a two-stage multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to evaluate e-payment systems in Ghana. The AHP method was utilized to find the contribution scores of the various criteria for the performance of the e-payment systems. With the aid of the Probability Linguistic-TOPSIS (PL-TOPSIS) approach, we obtained the performance scores of the e-payment systems and ranked them. Among the six indicators employed in this study, we found cost-effectiveness to be the major indicator of an e-payment system performance. The performance ranking results indicated that credit/debit card has the highest performance score, followed by mobile money, ATM, online banking, and E-zwitch, respectively. We contribute to literature by providing intuitions on how AHP and PL-TOPSIS methods can be applied to evaluate the performance of e-payment systems.

KEYWORDS

Electronic payment systems, Analytic Hierarchy process, Probabilistic linguistic-TOPSIS, Multi-criteria decision making analysis

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SENTIMENT ANALYSIS FOR MOVIES REVIEWS DATASET USING DEEP LEARNING MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Due to the enormous amount of data and opinions being produced, shared and transferred everyday across the internet and other media, Sentiment analysis has become vital for developing opinion mining systems. This paper introduces a developed classification sentiment analysis using deep learning networks and introduces comparative results of different deep learning networks. Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) was developed as a baseline for other networks results. Long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) in addition to a hybrid model of LSTM and CNN were developed and applied on IMDB dataset consists of 50K movies reviews files. Dataset was divided to 50% positive reviews and 50% negative reviews. The data was initially pre-processed using Word2Vec and word embedding was applied accordingly. The results have shown that, the hybrid CNN_LSTM model have outperformed the MLP and singular CNN and LSTM networks. CNN_LSTM have reported the accuracy of 89.2% while CNN has given accuracy of 87.7%, while MLP and LSTM have reported accuracy of 86.74% and 86.64 respectively. Moreover, the results have elaborated that the proposed deep learning models have also outperformed SVM, Naïve Bayes and RNTN that were published in other works using English datasets

KEYWORDS

Deep learning, LSTM, CNN, Sentiment Analysis, Movies Reviews, Binary Classification

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APPLYING NEURAL NETWORKS FOR SUPERVISED LEARNING OF MEDICAL DATA

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ABSTRACT

Constructing a classification model based on some given patterns is a form of learning from the environment perception. This modelling aims to discover new knowledge embedded in the input observations. Learning behaviour of the neural network model enhances the classification properties. This paper considers artificial neural networks for learning two different medical data sets in term of number of instances. The experiment results confirm that the back-propagation supervised learning algorithm has proved its efficiency for such non-linear classification issues.

KEYWORDS

Supervised learning, Artificial Neural Networks, Artificial intelligence, Learning, Classification

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